

THE AXIOLOGICAL CHARACTER OF DIDACTIC TOOLS DIRECTED TO PREPARE STUDENTS FOR THE FORMATION OF A CULTURE OF INTERNATIONAL COMMUNICATION IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, didactic tools aimed at the formation of international culture in students, their specific aspects, the nature of psychological processes of axiological and developmental character, and the pedagogic description mastered by future teachers are described. The article will serve as an important resource for future teachers, pedagogues, scientists, doctoral students, and independent researchers.

Key words: axiological, developmental, cognitive technologies, psychological processes, didactic tools, students, teachers, pedagogical process, higher education institutions, point of view, universal, moral qualities, educational process.

The process of preparing future teachers for the formation of a culture of interethnic communication in students should be manifested as a pedagogical process with a developmental character. There are a number of pedagogical factors influencing this process. In order to master the pedagogical activity related to the formation of the culture of interethnic communication in students, they must first have knowledge about the formation of life goals. Because life goals have the character of directing students.

In the process of preparing future teachers for pedagogical activity, it is important to form a healthy spiritual and pedagogical point of view in them towards inter-ethnic communication. In order to form a culture of inter-ethnic communication among students, future teachers need to acquire axiological knowledge and develop respect for values. For this purpose, it is necessary to form the skills of having a free choice and the experience of a valuable attitude towards representatives of different nationalities in the future teachers of society.

Today, when the foundations of the Third Renaissance are being laid, the formation of a culture of inter-ethnic communication among students is considered a national effort. For this purpose, it is necessary for future teachers to gain experience using approaches, concepts, and methods in the pedagogical process that help students form universal qualities. In order to acquire the culture of inter-ethnic communication, it is necessary to first learn the customs, traditions, religion, unique lifestyle, and linguistic resources of the

representatives of other nations and treat them with respect. In addition, future teachers should have the competence to design and organize pedagogical activities aimed at forming a culture of inter-ethnic communication among students. In addition, future teachers should be armed with methods of teaching students to feel national belonging and to respect the national belonging, traditions, and values of their peers.

The culture of inter-ethnic dialogue includes a system of human values, a civic perspective, a sense of independent, free living, recognition of the rights of all people living in a democratic society, a tolerant attitude towards representatives of other nationalities, and recognition and respect for their rights and values, nationalities, and religions. It includes such things as establishing a friendly relationship between them.

It is extremely necessary to convey to the minds of future teachers that the culture of interethnic communication among students is formed taking into account the stages of the pedagogical process and the levels of spiritual and cultural development of students. In order to form a culture of interethnic communication in students, future teachers should have the experience of paying attention to their psychological and physiological characteristics. They should be able to organize pedagogical situations that help students form a culture of interethnic communication, determine its main directions, and create opportunities to ensure the quality of the pedagogical process. In order for students to be ready to form a culture of interethnic communication, future teachers need to have clear knowledge and ideas about the effective organization of the educational process aimed at this goal, the control of its results, and the filling of gaps. Pedagogical processes aimed at teaching the mother tongue and foreign languages have special didactic opportunities for the formation of a culture of inter-ethnic communication in students. That is why it is important for future teachers studying in this field to acquire the competence to work in the pedagogical processes aimed at this goal.

In order to have the opportunity to freely move in a multicultural environment, to acquire knowledge and professional skills in the developed countries of the world, and to use the cultural wealth created by mankind as fully as possible, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan has taken "measures to bring the popularization of learning foreign languages to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan." According to the decision No. PQ-5117 of May 19, 2021, and the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 312 of May 19, 2021, "On measures to effectively

organize the popularization of learning foreign languages", No. 34 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 19, 2022, "Decisions on additional measures to improve the learning of foreign languages" serve as a program for the formation of the culture of international communication in the process of mastering foreign languages among students and pupils.

In order for future teachers to acquire the experience of forming the culture of inter-ethnic communication, they should first have the competence to select and present didactic tools that serve to enrich their cultural worldview.

In the 1980s of the 20th century, the formation of a culture of inter-ethnic communication among young people began to appear as a component of spiritual and moral education. The formation of a culture of interethnic communication among young people embodies the axiological, cognitive, and social-psychological directions of education.

Because the formation of a culture of inter-ethnic communication is a pedagogical activity of an axiological nature and is carried out based on the principle of humanitarianism, It embodies such values as love, naturalness, compassion, consistency, tolerance, equality, mutual respect, and trust towards people of other nationalities living in society. It is the sacred duty of a person to recognize the independence of each person, regardless of their nationality, to value their customs and traditions, and to respect the qualities of humanity.

The psychological processes of forming the culture of interethnic communication in students embody the thinking activity, imagination, memory, worldview, feelings, experiences, motives, will, and cognitive abilities of a person. This, in turn, accelerated the cultural and moral development of each individual. A person's morals, manners, and expression of his uniqueness, experiences, feelings, and intellectual level. The main directions of spiritual and moral education are expressed in the concept of developmental education. In this concept, a person's communicativeness and self-development abilities are prioritized. This, in turn, is a phenomenon that is the main focus in preparing future teachers for the formation of a culture of interethnic communication in students.

In society, the educational process and communication outside of it occupy a leading place in the spiritual and moral development of each person.

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